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**THE IMPACT OF CULTURAL SHOCK ON THE LIFE OF FOREIGN
STUDENTS IN UKRAINE**

The education system in Comoros is modeled by the former colonizer, France. After secondary education it is possible to follow a very accurate but limited University training, for this reason many Comorians students are leaving home and travelling abroad to study. Leaving and travelling to study in the new country can be stressful experience. Many students are surprised when they experience the impact of shock culture, and it can be helpful to realize your experience. It is actually quite normal.

Culture shock describes the impact of moving from a familiar culture (example my Comorian culture based on Islamic rules and African influences) to one that is unfamiliar culture (Ukrainian culture based on Eastern Orthodox, Slavic mythology and atheism). It includes the shock of new environment, meeting lots of new people and learning the way of a new country. It also includes the shock of being separated from the important people in our life, such as family, friends, colleagues and teachers: people we would talk to at times of uncertainty, people who give us support and guidance.

For example, our climate is extremely different from Ukrainian. Many Comorians students and I find the Eastern climate can affect us a lot, especially during the winter months when temperatures can reach minus 20 degrees. I was faced with increasingly colder and icier days. Whatever the reason I have chosen to study in Ukraine it is important that student prepares himself for the winter conditions. When winter comes around the days are both shorter and darker. So it helps to work out what time of day I tend to absorb the information better. During the winter my body will naturally feel more tired, as it starts to crave some warmth and comfort away from cold air. For any students in winter the temptation to sleep all day and procrastinate will be higher than usual, so I advise to keep your energy levels up. It is not easy to keep up us with a healthy diet when we're in the middle of our studies, but winter time can make it even more important to eat earlier and the right foods. I tried to prepare meals in advance, as this will improve our time management and be sure to stock up on fruits. I was always hungry in winter and here in Ukraine I prepare my

meals myself without my mom or parents. However most of Comorians boys don't cook in our family. Only sister or mom cooks for the whole family.

As the days grow colder and darker, I decided getting amount of exercise and sport to help and relax my mind, leaving me with positive thoughts during my studies. However I had broken my leg and was so angry in winter.

The other problem is language. Listening and speaking in a new language is tiring. In class, I have trouble understanding the lecture and reading materials. People speak quickly and you may feel embarrassed to ask them to repeat what they said. If Ukrainian or Russian is not your first language, you may find you miss your home language.

In my case I studied Ukrainian language and I live in Kharkiv city where most of people speak Russian language and the youth don't like to speak Ukrainian language. This is one of my big problem. Only in my class that teachers speak Ukrainian once the lecture is up, and I go to the street people speak Russian and I get boring more and more.

If your spouse or partner has accompanied you to Ukraine, remember that the stress of the transition may cause struggles in your relationship. The transition to a new culture may be very difficult for your partner. Your partner may feel very isolated; he/she has been transplanted from your culture and separated from family and friends. Simple tasks can be stressful due to the language barrier. Often times they do not have opportunities to engage in productive, meaningful activity such as pursuing a degree, and it may be more difficult for them to make new friends. For example, one of my Comorian student lives here with his spouse. They face the relationship stress, they don't go anywhere except to their lectures. They don't have any Ukrainian friends still be stressful due to the language and get new friends.

In conclusion, one can say that cultural shock can be overcome. The ways of overcoming can be different: for some students, these are new friends, sports, social activity, for others, intensive study, the desire to get excellent professional training.

ВПЛИВ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ШОКУ НА ЖИТТЯ ІНОЗЕМНИХ СТУДЕНТІВ В УКРАЇНІ

Розвідку присвячено вивченню проблем адаптації іноземних студентів в умовах чужого лінгвокультурного середовища. Мета дослідження – з'ясувати ознаки культурного шоку і шляхи його подолання. Встановлено причини виникнення культурного шоку (відмінності клімату, їжі, поведінки, мови, релігії, традицій, звичаїв, менталітету різних народів; відокремленість від рідних людей, соціальна ізоляція тощо). Схарактеризовано можливі шляхи подолання культурного шоку, налагодження академічного й суспільного життя, міжкультурних відносин.

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The work is devoted to the study of problems foreign students adaptation in the conditions of foreign linguistic and cultural environment. The purpose of research is to find out the features of culture shock and how to overcome it. The causes of culture shock (differences in climate, food, behavior, language, religion, traditions, customs, mentality of different peoples; isolation from native people, social exclusion, etc.) have been identified. Possible ways of overcoming cultural shock, establishing academic and social life, and intercultural relations are characterized.